

Full-length Acknowledgements

Doctoral Thesis – Michel Rouleau-Dick – Åbo Akademi University

Dear reader,

I imagine that if you are here, it's probably because you hope to read your name in this section, and I apologize in advance if you do not find it. The truth is that I have incurred a completely unrepayable debt to so many in the course of bringing this doctoral degree to fruition that it is simply impossible to include all those who helped me along the way. That being said, I'll do my best.

Firstly, I would like to thank my esteemed opponent, Professor Jane McAdam. This thesis would not have been possible without her groundbreaking work, and so it is a great honor to have had the opportunity to have her read and comment on my work. I would also like to extend my thanks to Assistant professor Miriam Cullen, for her valuable comments as part of the review process.

Secondly, dear reader, I want to thank my supervisors. As a matter of fact, I will take the opportunity here to correct a great injustice, by finally thanking my supervisor, Professor Elina Pirjatanniemi. I say "finally" because while Elina was my master's thesis supervisor, I completely forgot to thank her in my acknowledgements back then, and so my thanks actually extend as far back as 2016. Elina has always been a steadfast presence, a rare source of certainty in this always-shifting landscape of change and academic learning. Besides her sharp eye and always reliable common sense, I want to credit Elina for being instrumental in creating a warm, supportive research and teaching environment that has made the process of writing this thesis such a fruitful one. Also, her competence as a chair in many meetings throughout the last years can be credited with freeing up a not insignificant amount of time for research. My second supervisor, Professor Magdalena Kmak, also deserves a very special mention. Magda's astute comments and lack of tolerance for wordy texts and convoluted arguments has been a constant force for improvement while writing this thesis (and a clear contribution to its readability). Her mastery of a wide breadth of approaches to international law and her willingness to share her knowledge and discuss have also been a refreshing influence when trying to navigate the complex world of legal methodology. Magda's influence on this thesis also goes beyond it's academic content, and her excellent suggestions of Polish pickles and TV series also deserve a special mention. Lastly, and while his name may not appear formally as a supervisor on this thesis, I want to give special thanks to Docent Viljam Engström. Ville's incredible ability to give relevant and constructive comments on almost any topic was a significant asset while writing this thesis and the articles it includes. A keen coffee drinker, I think Ville's coffee room discussions should also get a specific shout out for their help in shaping some elements of this thesis. Overall (and I'm aware this paragraph is getting dangerously long now), the one thing that comes to mind when I think of my supervisors is something that is unfortunately not as present as it should be in academia, and that is generosity.

Completing a doctoral degree can be a lonely journey, and days and months can pass without significant, visible progress. Fortunately for me, in the good and bad moments, I have always been able to rely on the tightly-knit community at the Institute for Human Rights and the "extended family" around it. The team I have been a part of has been both incredibly competent, but also supportive at all the stages of the journey and I cannot emphasize enough how important that is. Even as early as 2013, when I was just an exchange student, I was impressed by the kindness shown to me by the teachers and their passion

in sharing their knowledge. Catarina Krause deserves special recognition for this and for creating an excellent study environment. By extension, I also want to thank all those who have contributed to teaching at the Institute. Creating solid bases and perpetuating the enthusiasm they bring to their teaching is a crucial element in motivating students to continue further in their studies, career or research, and it is unfortunate that this essential contribution is often not given the credit it deserves. In addition to Catarina, I want to highlight the competency and passion of Mikaela Heikkilä, Lisa Grans, Elvis Fokala, Maija Mustaniemi-Laakso and all the others I may be forgetting. I also acknowledge with gratitude the support of Professor Markku Suksi, and of all the members of the School of Law at Åbo Akademi.

Another incredibly supportive group that has been instrumental in completing this doctoral journey and that I want to thank is my fellow doctoral researchers at the Institute for Human Rights and School of Law. I have been lucky to have Stephen Phillips as my office neighbour for most of my doctoral studies and I'm not ashamed to say that these last years would have been very different without him around to discuss both scholarly and less scholarly topics (cc Meiraf Tesfaye and Dionysia Kang). Steve's generosity with his time and willingness to share his experience with the workings of Åbo Akademi's sometimes labyrinthine HR was a game changer more than once. More than a colleague, I'm happy to count Steve as a good friend and an incredibly competent scholar. Dionysia Kang has also been another "partner in crime" and an always welcome presence at the Institute. It is not always easy to stay yourself in the challenging environment of academia, but the example of Dionysia's strong moral compass and dedication to her research have been a reliable source of inspiration. But that's just part of the picture, and the truth is that Dionysia is always fun to be around and a great partner to brainstorm anything, ranging from research ideas to Christmas door decoration ideas. I also want to thank Meiraf Tesfaye for her support throughout this project. Meiraf's enthusiasm to discuss and challenge assumptions is always appreciated, and her excellent mastery of the law often makes such a discussion a risky endeavour. It always feels a little inadequate to include Maija Mustaniemi-Laakso in the doctoral researchers (and I'm sure this will be the case for only a very short period of time after the publication of this thesis), but here we are. The reason for this is that Maija could just as easily be a grant-writer, a professor, event planner, project manager, or a research consultant, in addition to being a kind and thoughtful person. Maija's attention to detail and extensive knowledge of human rights law have been an aspirational goal throughout this doctoral journey, and her and Mikaela's work have acted as a reliable gold-standard for any ongoing research. I take the opportunity here to thank Yulia Dergacheva in these acknowledgements. Although Yulia is based at the University of Turku, she more than deserves a mention here for her friendship over the years, as well as for the delicious food, mushroom-picking skills, and all the laughs. I will also include here Dr. Lisa Grans, since she paved the way for article-based theses at Åbo Akademi, and for her openness to share her experiences of the doctoral journey. Any scholarly work builds upon a complex pyramid of knowledge, but it is easy to forget the power of functional knowledge, of knowing how to proceed and how to navigate the treacherous waters of academic publishing. Lisa and all the others at the Institute for Human Rights deserve special thanks for their valuable advice. I want to conclude by thanking Thomas Heikell, Isabell Junkkari, Albert Vlodder, Eleonora Del Gaudio, and all the other doctoral researchers and researchers I have crossed path with, and who have made this doctoral journey a lively and stimulating process.

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